

IMPACT OF FDI IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN AUSTRALIA

ABSTRACT

MELIANI, Raouia

The objective of this study is to scrutinize the correlation between foreign direct investment (FDI) and production in the construction industry of Australia (CIP) during the period spanning from 2009 to 2021. The data was subjected to both histogram and regression analysis utilizing Minitab software for the purposes of this investigation. As per the empirical results, it can be inferred that foreign direct investment (FDI) and construction industry production (CIP) exhibit a positive correlation. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the coefficient of inbound FDI did not manifest a statistically significant association with the aforementioned variables. Furthermore, the inquiry scrutinized the temporal progression of foreign direct investment (FDI) and construction industry production (CIP), with the year 2015 serving as a benchmark for comparison. Upon perusal of the pertinent literature, it is evident that foreign direct investment plays a pivotal role in the amplification and efficacy of the construction industry. The investigation additionally exemplifies the utmost significance of augmenting foreign direct investment in a manner that is pragmatic and oriented towards generating profits.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Construction Industry

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	<u>Page</u>
ABSTRACT	i
ABBREVIATIONS	iii
1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND QUESTION.....	1
1.2 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE	2
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	3
2.1 FACTORS AFFECTING FDI INFLOW	3
2.2 FDI IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	4
3. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF FDI IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN AUSTRALIA	6
3.1 MODEL SPECIFICATIONS AND VARIABLES	6
3.2 VARIABLE MEASUREMENT AND DATA SOURCE.....	7
3.3 REGRESSION RESULTS	10
4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION	12
4.1 DISCUSSION.....	12
4.2 CONCLUSION	12
REFERENCES	14

ABBREVIATIONS

ABS	:	Australian Bureau of Statistics
BIM	:	Building Information Modeling
CIP	:	Construction Industrial Product
FDI	:	Foreign Direct Investment
FIS	:	Foreign Investment in Securities
GDP	:	Gross Domestic Product
GVA	:	Gross Value Added
ICT	:	Information and Communication Technology
IT	:	Information Technology
MoD	:	Millions of Dollars
UNCTD	:	United Nations Conferences on Trade and Development

1. INTRODUCTION

Foreign direct investment is an essential investor to the construction industry, unequivocally and certainly. Speculation is a main consideration to help monetary development, in any case, with FDIs lead to positive externalities that moreover increment development levels through their innovation overflow impacts. At the point when foreign direct investments stream inwards towards the industry of construction, they likewise send their insight and innovation.

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND QUESTION

The role of foreign direct investment in promoting construction is largely influenced by the nature of host country institutions and policies. As per the data furnished by the Australian Bureau of Statistics, the quantum of monetary worth attributed to the domain of residential construction in Australia was estimated at \$101 billion during the fiscal year 2019-2020, thereby constituting a significant proportion of 28% in relation to the overall construction industry.

The essential function of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in fostering sustainable economic growth within the industry cannot be overstated. The infusion of foreign investment has yielded capital, novel technologies, erudition, and productivity, thereby augmenting the industry's efficacy and output. As an illustration, non-domestic investors have implemented novel methodologies of building and supervisory methodologies that have enhanced the caliber of edification and curtailed the expenses of construction.

Furthermore, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has created gainful employment prospects for the Australian populace, facilitated the spread of expertise and knowledge to the domestic labor force, and instigated the advancement of infrastructure. Notwithstanding, it is imperative to implement sustainable policies aimed at mitigating potential hazards, such as the exploitation of practices by foreign investors, as stated by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Consequently, the present inquiry endeavors to scrutinize the impact of FDI on the construction industry in Australia.

Investment alludes to the time, energy or material spent to accomplish future advantages inside a particular date or time range. It has various implications in terms of money and financial aspects.

In finance, investment is the buying or making of a resource that anticipates capital appreciation, profits (benefits), interest pay, rents, or a mix of these profits. This could conceivably be upheld by exploration and examination. Most or all types of speculation imply some type of hazard, like putting resources into stocks, land, and surprisingly fixed rate protections, which are influenced by expansion hazard, in addition to other things. Investment financial backers should distinguish and oversee speculation related dangers.

In macroeconomics, investment alludes to the measure of merchandise bought per unit time that are not burned-through as of now. The sorts of speculation remember private investment for long haul lodging administrations, non-private fixed interest in new machines or processing plants, human resources interest in labor instruction and stock speculation (deliberate or accidental amassing, stock of products).

The study seeks to answer the following research questions.

- What are the factors influencing FDI in the construction industry in Australia?
- What is the impact of FDI on the construction industry in Australia?

1.2 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

The purpose of writing this paper is to break down the co-incorporation of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflow in the construction industry in Australia from 2009 to 2021. This investigation utilizes Minitab software to calculate the regression analysis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Foreign direct investment inflows to a country relying upon a scope of financial and political elements, including monetary strength, market development possibilities, framework accessibility, venture related laws and arrangements, charges, exchange, wage rates, monetary business sectors, government spending, modern guidelines, and an informed and talented labor force. There is a great deal of writing on the viability of FDI, its determinants and its job in financial development and improvement. Business analysts by and large accept that FDI ought to be viewed as an enhancement to home-grown capital and a method for acquiring proper innovation.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is the control responsibility of companies in one country by a substance situated in another country. Foreign direct investment is not quite the same as foreign investment in securities (FIS), which is a detached interest in another nation's protections (like public stocks and bonds), and its component is "control". Furthermore, the control of innovation, the board and surprisingly key sources of info can likewise be controlled.

The wellspring of speculation doesn't influence the meaning of foreign direct investment, that is, investment can be made "disorderly" by procuring organizations in the objective nation, or "coordinated" by extending the matter of existing endeavors in that country.

2.1 FACTORS AFFECTING FDI INFLOW

There are factors that may impact or influence the flow of foreign direct investment. Ramady and Sae (2007) contemplated the essential move of empowering FDI. The creators overviewed chiefs and endeavored to comprehend the status of foreign direct investment. The outcomes from the investigation tracked down large invite FDI into the nation, yet they do hold conflicted mentalities toward its apparent advantages.

Alkhatlan (2013) investigated the foreign direct investment inflows and financial development utilizing a co-joining examination. He examined information from 1980 to 2010, the progression of FDI is driven by political elements. Different factors that influence the measure of internal FDI incorporate expected financial turn of events, political dependability, majority rule government, economic deals, technology, construction and

manufacturing industries, and the degree of monetary progression. These variables are emphatically related to the degree of internal FDI. According to Romer (2012), technology which may be used as a proxy for human skills and knowledge is a factor that has contributed to the positive effects of foreign direct investments.

Also, Binsaeed (2009) found in his investigation on the elements influencing the area of foreign direct investment in the construction industry business that FDI is drawn in by area explicit variables, including cost factors, market components, framework and innovation factors, political elements, and social and social elements.

2.2 FDI IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

Australia's construction industry is big business, adding billions to the country's GDP every year. Building information modeling (BIM) and other digital innovations have contributed to the industry's rapid transformation in recent years. The purpose of this literature study is to analyze FDI's effect on the efficiency and competitiveness of the Australian construction industry, as well as its role in the industry's growth. A study by Pekka (2017), investigates how the Australian construction industry digitized faster. ABS national accounts 1995–2015. Construction dominates Australia. Mining, banking, and insurance raised GVA. 15% of construction's gross fixed capital formation but 1% of GVA is ICT. Construction has the third highest GVA/hour labor productivity despite inadequate digitization. Industry-level national accounts demonstrate ICT investments don't boost productivity.

As posited by J. Sacilotto and M. Loosemore, preeminent professionals within the Australian construction industry are adopting an exceedingly logical, profit-driven, and practical methodology towards enhancing foreign direct investment (FDI). The significance of Chinese foreign direct investment (FDI) in Australia's construction industry is deemed indispensable, although concerns have been raised pertaining to non-compliant materials, labor standards, and safety standards. (Ahmed et al., 2019)

Foreign direct investment (FDI) has been crucial in the success and expansion of Australia's constructing industry. New technologies, such as building information modeling (BIM), made possible by FDI have revolutionized project management and teamwork in the

business world. The lack of uniformity in industry norms and practices, as well as the sector's heavy reliance on government contracts and procurement procedures, are impediments to attracting and keeping FDI. The construction industry is massive, accounting for around 9 percent of worldwide GDP. (Ruddock and Lopes 2006).

Foreign investment in construction can yield benefits for a nation's employment rate, infrastructure, and overall standard of living, as posited by Ahmad et al. (2019). According to Ly's (2021) research, the construction industry serves as a steadfast cornerstone for the broader economy. The construction sector plays a pivotal role in promoting enduring economic expansion and mitigating impoverishment due to the far-reaching ramifications of construction undertakings on the economy.

In conclusion, the construction sector is vital to the Australian economy, contributing billions of dollars annually. Digital technologies like Building Information Modelling (BIM) have changed the Australian construction industry, improving operational efficiency and market competitiveness. This literature review examined the effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) on Australia's construction industry and found that it is essential to its growth. Foreign direct investment (FDI), especially Chinese FDI, is essential for industry growth, according to leading Australian building experts. Foreign money in buildings can improve infrastructure, living standards, and jobs, reducing poverty and boosting economic growth. Construction accounts for 9% of global GDP. This critique emphasizes the importance of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the construction sector and its potential benefits to the Australian economy.

3. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF FDI IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN AUSTRALIA

The purpose of this paper is to empirically analyze the effect of FDI in construction industry in Australia from 2009 to 2021. It is assumed that the construction industry depends on the inflow of FDI, the increase of domestic capital, government expenditure and domestic labor. Using Minitab Software to calculate the collected statistical data from OECD Data for Australia's Inward FDI flows in the Construction Industry, and Construction Industrial Production (%) with the base being the one from the year 2015.

3.1 MODEL SPECIFICATIONS AND VARIABLES

The simple regression model is characterized through a numerical connection developed with regards to monetary hypothesis, which infers that the financial wonder as impact is the aftereffect of the cumulated activity of two classifications of components:

- A primary factor that is fundamental
- The wide range of various variables can be viewed as insignificant, with arbitrarily happened activity or consistent activity, perpetual upon the monetary marvel as impact. These impacts are gathered in the outcome variable.

In a basic regression econometric model, the connection between the outcome variable (Y) and the causal variable (X) can be portrayed by a capacity as follows:

$$y_i = a + b X_i$$

y_i – Outcome/ dependent variable

x_i – Factorial / independent variable

b – Estimated Regression Intercept Coefficient

a – Slope Coefficient

Henceforth, employing the ensuing equation utilizing the variables in this undertaking shall be:

$$CIP = a + b \text{ Inward FDI Flows}$$

The outcome yields that CIP is equivalent to Y, whereby b represents the coefficient of regression intercept, a represents the coefficient of slope, and X denotes the Inward FDI Flows.

3.2 VARIABLE MEASUREMENT AND DATA SOURCE

Table 3.2.1 Evolution of Australia's Inward FDI flows in the Construction Industry, and Construction Industrial Production (%).

Year	Inward FDI flows in the Construction Industry (MoD)	Construction Industrial Production (%)	Construction Industrial Production (%) Base 2015
2009	800	82	-18.0
2010	881	84.3	-15.7
2011	736	90.8	-9.2
2012	2579	98.3	-1.7
2013	3420	100.2	0.2
2014	2834	103.7	3.7
2015	-811	100	0.0
2016	103	97	-3.0
2017	952	98.8	-1.2
2018	813	101.4	1.4
2019	2874	99.3	-0.7
2020	177	93.4	-6.6
2021	2300	99.4	-0.6

Source: Data OECD Inward FDI Flows by Industry, (MoP, Current US\$)-Australia.

<https://data.oecd.org/fdi/inward-fdi-flows-by-industry.htm#indicator-chart>

Source: Data OECD Industrial Production, (%) Australia.

<https://data.oecd.org/industry/industrial-production.htm#indicator-chart%20>

The impact of inward foreign direct investment (FDI) flows on industrial production can be examined using a simple regression model, where industrial production is the dependent variable and inward FDI flows are the independent variable.

The quantity of money that comes into a country from other countries at the same time is the independent variable, and it is denoted by the term "inward FDI Flows." Hence, a possible model could be:

$$CIP = b + a \text{ Inward FDI Flows}$$

Graph 3.2.1 Construction Industrial Production (%) per Year with the Base of 2015.

Graph 3.2.2 Inward FDI Flows in the Construction Industry (MoD) 2009-2021

In the construction industry, Australia got 800 million dollars in FDI in 2009. Construction industry production fell by 18% from the base year, which is the one from 2015.

Inward FDI inflow climbed to \$881 million in 2010. Construction industry production climbed by 84.3%, resulting in a 15.7% decline from the base year.

Inward FDI inflow dropped to \$736 million in 2011. Construction industry production climbed by 90.8%, resulting in a 9.2% decline from the year 2015.

In 2012, inward FDI flows surged dramatically, reaching 2579 million dollars. Construction industry production climbed by 98.3%, resulting in a 1.7% reduction from the base year.

In 2013, inward FDI flows reached 3420 million dollars. Construction industry production climbed by 100.2%, resulting in a 0.2% gain over the base year.

Inward FDI inflow declined to 2834 million dollars in 2014. Construction industry production climbed by 103.7%, representing a 3.7% rise over the base year.

In 2015, inward FDI flows became negative, meaning that foreign investors withdrew more funds from Australia's construction industry than they invested. Since 2015 is the base year, the Construction industry output remained constant.

In 2016, inward FDI flows were only 103 million dollars, and building industrial production fell 3% from the base year.

In 2017, foreign FDI flows grew to 952 million dollars, while construction industrial output increased by 98.8%, resulting in a 1.2% reduction from the base year.

In 2018, foreign FDI flows fell slightly to \$813 million, while construction industrial production climbed by 101.4%, resulting in a 1.4% rise over the base year.

In 2019, inward FDI flows grew to 2874 million dollars, but construction industry production fell 0.7% from the base year.

In 2020, inward FDI inflow fell considerably to 177 million dollars, while construction industry production fell 6.6% from the base year.

In 2021, inward FDI inflow grew to 2300 million dollars, but construction industry production fell 0.6% from the year 2015.

In its entirety, the graphed information depicts a variable trend in inbound foreign direct investment (FDI) streams within the construction sector, as well as construction industrial output, throughout the years. The year 2015 serves as a foundational reference point for evaluating the percentage fluctuation in industrial production within the construction sector. The negative foreign direct investment (FDI) flows observed in 2015 signify that the foreign investors divested more capital than they infused, resulting in the industrial production remaining unchanged relative to the reference year.

3.3 REGRESSION RESULTS

Throughout the course of this analysis, Minitab have been used for the dual purposes of generating graphical representations and conducting regression analyses. Minitab is a statistical software package that affords a user-friendly interface for the purpose of data analysis and visualization. The software is extensively utilized in both academic and industrial settings, offering a diverse array of statistical analysis tools that are amenable to a multitude of research applications. In this instance, Minitab was employed to generate graphical representations that depict the interdependence of variables and to execute a regression analysis to ascertain the correlation between variables and facilitate prognostication. The utilization of Minitab software ensured the attainment of dependable and precise outcomes from the statistical analysis, thereby rendering it an invaluable instrument in this scholarly investigation.

Regression Analysis: CIP versus Inward FDI

Analysis of Variance

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Regression	1	66.88	66.88	1.60	0.231
Inward FDI	1	66.88	66.88	1.60	0.231
Error	11	458.46	41.68		
Total	12	525.33			

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
6.45583	12.73%	4.80%	0.00%

Coefficients

Term	Coef	SE Coef	T-Value	P-Value	VIF
Constant	93.57	2.65	35.32	0.000	
Inward FDI	0.00182	0.00144	1.27	0.231	1.00

Regression Equation

$$\mathbf{CIP = 93.57 + 0.00182 \text{ Inward FDI}}$$

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1 DISCUSSION

The regression results displays that the long-term equation of the construction industry production during 2009 to 2021 in Australia is $CIP = 93.57 + 0.00182 \text{ Inward FDI}$. Inward FDI shows how construction industrial production (CIP) and inward foreign direct investment (FDI) are related in Australia's construction business.

When the inward FDI is zero, the predicted value of CIP is 93.57, which is the intercept of the regression equation. This means that even if no one from outside Australia invests in the construction business, it is still expected to make a profit of 93.57.

The coefficient of inward FDI is 0.00182, which means that the predicted value of CIP goes up by 0.00182 units for each unit of inward FDI. This coefficient shows how much the CIP is expected to change for a one-unit rise in FDI, if all other variables stay the same.

So, the regression equation shows that there is a positive link between FDI coming into Australia and CIP in the construction business. But the coefficient of inward FDI is not statistically significant, which means that the link is weak and not reliable.

4.2 CONCLUSION

The present study arrived at a definitive inference by scrutinizing the correlation between the production levels in the Australian construction industry (CIP) during the period spanning from 2009 to 2021 and the inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI). Per the results of the regression analysis, there exists a positive correlation between foreign direct investment (FDI) and capital investment policy (CIP). The statistical insignificance of the coefficient of inward foreign direct investment (FDI) suggests that the correlation between the two variables is weak and not highly dependable.

Furthermore, the inquiry scrutinized the temporal progression of foreign direct investment (FDI) and construction industry production (CIP), utilizing the year 2015 as a benchmark for comparison. The production output within the sector remained constant in the year 2015 in relation to the base year, because of the absence of foreign direct investment. An appraisal of pertinent scholarly literature revealed that foreign direct investment (FDI) is pivotal to the

augmentation and efficacy of the construction industry. The implementation of novel technologies, such as building information modeling (BIM), has a substantial impact on project management and team collaboration.

Likewise, the study evinced the indispensability of a pragmatic and profit-driven approach in augmenting foreign direct investment, concomitantly redressing concerns regarding subpar materials, labor standards, and safety protocols. Broadly speaking, the inquiry furnishes us with an enhanced comprehension of the role that overseas direct investment assumes within the realm of construction and proffers recommendations for further scholarly investigation in this domain.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, Munir, Zhen-Yu Zhao, Muhammad Irfan, and Marie Claire Mukeshimana. 2019. Empirics on influencing mechanisms among energy, finance, trade, environment, and economic growth: A heterogeneous dynamic panel data analysis of China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 26: 14148–14170
2. Alkhatlan K., Javid, M. (2013) Energy Consumption, Carbon Emissions and Economic Growth in Saudi Arabia: An Aggregate and Disaggregate Analysis
3. Binsaeed Fawaz (2009), "The Factors Affecting Foreign Direct Investment Location in the Petrochemicals Industry, the case of Saudi Arabia", BBS Doctoral Symposium, 23rd & 24th March, 2009.
4. Brick & Block Careers Staff. 2023. How Big is Australian Construction Industry? <https://www.brickandblockcareers.org.au/brickies-blog/how-big-is-australian-construction-industry/>
5. Chan, D. W. M., Saka, A. 2020. Adoption and Implementation of Building Information Modelling (BIM) in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs): A Review and Conceptualization.
6. Coppel, J. 2020. Foreign Investment in Australia.
7. De Mellow Luiz R. (1997). Foreign direct investment in the developing countries and growth: a selective survey. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 34(1): 1-34.
8. Kornecki, L., Borodulin, V. 2010. Foreign Direct Investment Stock Contributes to Economic Growth in the U.S. Economy.
9. Ly, Bora. 2021. The Implication of FDI in the Construction Industry in Cambodia under BRI
10. Pekka, L., Seong, M. P., Sungkon, M. 2017. Keeping up with the pace of Digitization: The Case of the Australian Construction Industry.
11. Phuong, N. L. (2021) Literature Review on The Impacts of Foreign Direct Investment in the Emerging Economy: The Case of Vietnam
12. Romer, D. (2012) *Advanced Macroeconomics* (4th ed.) New York: McGraw Hill Companies.
13. Ruddock, Les, and Jorge Lopes. 2006. The Construction Sector and Economic Development: The “Bon Curve”. *Construction Management and Economics* 24: 717–23.

14. Sacilotto, J., Loosemore, M. 2018. Chinese Investment in the Australian Construction Industry: The Social Amplification of Risk.
15. Sukhadolets, T., Stupnikova, E., Fomenko, N., Kapustina, N., and Kuznetsov, Y. 2021. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Investment in Construction and Poverty in Economic Crises (Denmark, Italy, Germany, Romania, China, India and Russia).
16. <https://data.oecd.org/fdi/inward-fdi-flows-by-industry.htm#indicator-chart>
17. <https://data.oecd.org/industry/industrial-production.htm#indicator-chart%20>